

**AGENT-BASED
SUPPORT TOOL FOR
THE DEVELOPMENT
OF AGRICULTURE POLICIES**

D9.6 AGRICORE Video

Deliverable Number	D9.6
Lead Beneficiary	AXIA Innovation
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Work package	WP9
Delivery Date	M24
Dissemination Level	Public

www.agricore-project.eu

The Agricore project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No. 816078

Document Information

Project title	Agent-based support tool for the development of agriculture policies
Project acronym	AGRICORE
Project call	H2020-RUR-04-2018-2019
Grant number	816078
Project duration	1.09.2019-31.8.2023 (48 months)

Version History

Version	Description	Organisation	Date
1.0	AGRICORE Video deliverable	AXIA Innovation, Exelisis	M24

Executive Summary

The AGRICORE project is developing a highly modular computational tool, introducing various novel elements in agricultural policy modeling due to its use of state-of-the-art modeling techniques and ICT advancements. This tool aims to contribute to improving policy design, as well as facilitate agricultural impact assessment and monitoring.

Within the framework of AGRICORE's WP9-related activities, particularly in Task 9.3: Communication Activities, it is foreseen to develop the official video of the AGRICORE project in order to communicate the project objectives and the potential impact for policymakers and researchers. AXIA Innovation was in charge of the production of the video and this report aims to describe the methodology applied which led to the final result.

Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Full Name
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
RTD	Research, Technology and Development
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprise

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1 Introduction

This deliverable presents the methodology followed by AXIA Innovation in order to produce the official AGRICORE video as part of the dissemination and communication activities of the project. The video serves as a presentational tool which will be utilized for the effective communication of AGRICORE's concept and objectives towards the relevant stakeholders. The video is available on YouTube and at the official AGRICORE website. It is intended to be showcased at the various dissemination activities implemented by the AGRICORE consortium such as the participation in conferences, seminars, workshops, or other similar events remotely or physical.

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- Concept of the video
- Script of the video
- Target Audience
- Description of the technical production
- Final release of the video

2 The Video

2.1 Concept

The idea behind the AGRICORE video is to communicate the project objectives and the potential impact for policymakers and researchers. The video is a powerful, effective part of the AGRICORE marketing strategy and boosts the awareness, interest, and interaction of all the different stakeholder groups within the project. The video has a conceptual character, explaining the EU's need for better policy design tools for evidence-based and transparent agricultural policies which will be in line with the CAP's objectives. Furthermore, the video describes how the proposed AGRICORE tool will contribute towards the improvement of the up to date agricultural modelling tools by highlighting its main features and advantages such as farm heterogeneity, fine geographical scales and its open source character facilitating, thus, easy collaboration for further development and high customization potential.

2.2 Script

The first version of the script was written by AXIA Innovation while the final version was produced collaboratively with the precious input of IDENER.

Script:

The common agricultural policy or CAP aims to foster a sustainable and competitive agricultural sector that can contribute significantly towards a stable economic future for farmers and rural areas while at the same time act upon climate change and environmental hurdles.

That's why the CAP, is the European Union's largest budget item. In 2019, the almost €60 billion budget of the CAP covered the support for farmer's incomes, ensured the supply of quality food, protected biodiversity, and encouraged young people into farming. In 2020 the CAP accounted around 34.5% of EU budget (EUR 58.12 billion).

However, the design of evidence-based and transparent agricultural policies which will incorporate all objectives of the CAP is a long process involving the assessment of various local and global parameters. Therefore, the EC has identified the need for better policy design. Although farmers are increasingly active in policy making and policy makers are more and more familiar with rural issues, agricultural models are needed to describe and interpret key aspects of agricultural policy design, assisting in the CAP instruments implementation.

The most widely used models up to date compute the equilibrium between aggregate production and aggregate demand to calculate the impact on farmers' profitability and the price paid by consumers. The problem with this type of models is that, when aggregating, they do not take into account the heterogeneity of European farms, so that some measures that are shown to be beneficial at the aggregate level in the model, may be harmful at the particular level for some types of producers or particular regions.

The AGRICORE project aims to offer a solution.

The AGRICORE project is an EC funded research project which will make use of state-of-the-art computational technology advancements and agent-based modelling techniques for the design of such models. This will allow new extended capabilities to capture farm heterogeneity, to address a finer geographical scale and to assess the effects of CAP in a systematic and efficient way.

The goal is to improve the capacity to design new policies, incorporate assessment instruments for the social, economic, and environmental impacts of those new policies, and be able to do so in various geographical scales: from regional to global scale.

For this purpose, 11 partners are joining forces in the AGRICORE project, coming from 6 different European countries (Spain, Germany, Italy, Greece, Poland and Turkey), including companies (4 SMEs, 1 LE, 1 Association) and academia (1 RTD and 4 Universities).

The AGRICORE tool will test the improved modelling capabilities in 3 use cases, looking both to make predictions before policies are implemented (ex-ante analysis) and to evaluate the policies' impact after their implementation (ex-post analysis).

The use cases of Andalusia, Poland and Greece have been selected, as they incorporate differences in geographical scales and policy instruments in focus, making themselves the perfect candidates for testing and developing the tool.

The AGRICORE tool will act as a highly modular and customizable suite using data from several European databases and incorporating the knowledge of many biophysical modules. Furthermore, it will be released as an open-source project. In this way, all interested institutions and researchers will be able to update and improve the tool in the future in a transparent way, as well as to apply it in use cases of interest.

Given all the above, AGRICORE will significantly contribute towards the design of better CAP instruments, assisting policy makers to perform evidence-based policy design, but also policy evaluation. This will embrace the objectives of the CAP for improving the lives of farmers and rural area development while simultaneously act upon climate and environmental challenges thus, creating a sustainable, competitive, and productive european agricultural sector.

For more information visit the AGRICORE website [AGRICORE project website \(agricore-project.eu\)](http://agricore-project.eu) and don't forget to follow us on Social Media

- LinkedIn: [AGRICORE Project](#)
- Twitter: [AGRICORE Project](#)
- Facebook: [AGRICORE Project](#)

2.3 Target Audience

The main target audience are policymakers in the field of agriculture on regional, national and european level as well as researcher involved in the field of policy modelling, agent- based modelling and ICT. These groups are the key stakeholders of AGRICORE and the potential users of the AGRICORE tool. Accordingly, the script of the video targets to explain not only the need for policy modelling and evaluation tools within the EU but also to describe the technical features and advancements introduced by the AGRICORE tool.

2.4 Technical production

The technical production of the video follows several specific steps that are outlined below.

1. **Writing of the script.** The script of the AGRICORE video was written by AXIA Innovation and revised by the Coordinator IDENER. It was agreed that the script should explain the need which AGRICORE targets to cover through developing this novel tool for the design of evidenced based and transparent agricultural policies as well as the features and novelties under development. Furthermore, the script describes the use cases implemented during the project for validation of the functionality of the tool and the expected impact on rural development and farmers.
2. **Recording.** The next step is the recording (voiceover) of the script which was implemented at a recording studio. Once the final version of the recording was compiled, audio editing was necessary in order to harmonize the whole sound of the recording (harmonizing the voice of the speaker etc.)
3. **Music.** Once the final version of the recording was compiled, the right background music needed to be chosen and synchronized with the recording.
4. **Footage.** The next step was to find the appropriate footage that fits the theme of the script in various repositories such as [envato elements](#). In the case of AGRICORE, also inhouse footage was used.
5. **Synchronization.** As soon as the footage which had been selected was placed in the video timeline, the synchronization process of the final footage and the recording started.
6. **Graphics and text.** The last step included the addition of graphical elements and text to the video highlighting the most important aspects of the script, catching the interest of the viewer as well as and ensuring that special attention will be paid to the crucial parts.

For the production of the video various tools have been used such as the Adobe Creative Suite which consists of various applications. In particular, Premier Pro has been used for editing the footage and the audio while Adobe After Effects and Adobe Illustrator was used for the graphics of the video.

2.5 Release

The video is available on YouTube under: <https://youtu.be/SdX12tGZI8Q> with 220 views and at the official AGRICORE website under: <https://agricore-project.eu/>. Furthermore, the video has been shared on all 3 social media accounts of AGRICORE in order to maximize further the impact.

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6838367428422987776>

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/AGRICOREPROJECT>

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/AgricoreP/status/1432603391398719488>

3 Conclusion

AGRICORE is a promising high-impact EU-funded research project with novel objectives that need to be communicated as effectively as possible to all the relevant stakeholders, from policy makers and researchers to farmers and society. The AGRICORE video aims to illustrate in a creative and descriptive way the objectives, the concept as well as the advancements introduced by the AGRICORE tool under development. The main target audience however with this video are policy makers and researchers of the field as the tool is being developed primarily for their needs. Further communication activities are being implemented in order to convey AGRICORE’s mission also to the wider public.

Within this report, the target was to present the work performed in order to produce the official video of the project starting from the concept to the technical production and ending with the official release of the video in various platforms ensuring a wide promotion of the project and its research efforts.

